

Comparative Analysis between School-Effectiveness-Variables and Achievement in Quantitative Economics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Osun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the extent to which School Effectiveness variables predict secondary school student's academic achievements in quantitative Economics in Osun State. The study adopted non-experimental research design of correlational type. The population of the study consists of all government senior secondary schools class two Economics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Osun state. A sample size of 1080 students (male 445 and female 635) were selected from the target population using multistage sampling technique. Results from the study revealed a positive relationship among school administrative practice, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos and students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics. Findings also revealed that School effectiveness variables significantly predict students' academic achievement in quantitative Economics ($R = 0.322, P < 0.05$). It was concluded that School Effectiveness variables significantly contributed to prediction of students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics. The study recommended that school administrative practices should be properly set by the school leaders, school activities should not be overlooked by the school administrators and school learning culture should be officially guided by a written template to improve students' academic achievement.

Keywords: School Effectiveness, Students' Academic Achievement and Quantitative Economics

Introduction

School is generally perceived as the centre of learning, where knowledge and ideas are generated and shared, to ease human standard of living. A wide acceptable school of thought refers to school as a place where effective mankind is nurtured to contribute effectively to societal development. Also larger percentage of formal education is received in the school. Therefore education is expected to make man more effective. Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014) expects that education in Nigeria should among others, contribute to national development through high-level relevant manpower training, acquisition of both physical and intellectual skills which will enable individuals to be self-reliant and useful members of the society, promoting and encouraging scholarship and community service, forging and cementing national unity, promoting national and international understanding and interactions, developing the intellectual capability of individuals to understand and appreciate their local and external environments, developing and inculcating proper values for the survival of individuals and the society.

In order to achieve the aforementioned tasks, Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) in May, 2008 introduced new senior secondary school curriculum, which commenced in September, 2011. The curriculum was planned to consolidate new basic education programme in the area of human capital development. Economics as one of the elective subjects offered in the senior secondary school is considered appropriate to actualise the dreams outlined by NERDC, particularly on human capital development.

Economics as social science subject plays a significant role in human capital development; it sensitizes students about ways to minimize cost and maximize benefit. It goes a long way to explain the ways by which man can make rational decisions on ways of doing things. Economics as a social science subject, serves as the basis for understanding the complexities of how resources are managed to minimize cost and waste with a view to yielding more benefits. The subject looks at how governments, businesses, societies, households and individuals make decisions about how, when and where to best use their resources. Economics involves many theoretical and conceptual models to study behaviour and predict how entities will respond to given changes in market conditions and fiscal policies, among other factors (Zhao, Li, Wang, Zhou & Luo, 2022). The subject builds mathematical models to formulate hypotheses where theories are derived to explain interactions among

contingences in human behaviours. The use of Mathematics in Economics allows economists to precisely define and test economic theories against real world data. Similarly, use of mathematics models allow Economics to make information to be concise, precise, and allows adequate treatment to the yet to be determined variables. Economic policies and decisions are rarely made without mathematical models; because mathematical models allow Economics concepts to be far away from ordinary abstractions as they present concepts in Economics in such a way that issues will be quantifiably presented.

In spite of the importance of Economics and the huge benefits derivable from using mathematical models and equations to explain human reactions and behaviours regarding ends and satisfactions. Previous studies over the years indicate that there are continuous under-achievement in Economics at the secondary school level, especially in the concepts that involve calculations and data responses. Obiezu (2018) reported that the academic performance of secondary school students in the Senior Secondary Certificate Examinations (SSCE) has taken a dramatic decline in recent times. According to Abubakar (2013) students' achievement in Economics fluctuates yearly. Besides, Akira (2013), Okoro (2013) and Duruji, Azuh and Oviasogie (2014) corroborate the fact that the declining in students' achievement worries parents, teachers, school administrators, and other stakeholders in the educational system in Nigeria. Indeed, the achievement did not measure up with other subjects when compared with the resources invested on education in general. Considering Economics as an important subject that exposes students to developmental issues, the under-achievement of students in the subject call for investigation and remediation, despite the enormous government investments on education in Osun state.

Studies in and outside of Nigeria are concerned about the problem of under-achievement of students in Economics, but much has not been done in some areas, particularly in the section A of paper II of Economics questions that involves statistics and mathematical concepts, which is referred to as Quantitative Economics. In addition, WAEC Chief Examiner's reports pointed out that, students' performances in the essay part of Economics examination (section A) are not encouraging. It was reported that students had poor understanding of data presentation and basic mathematical skills to tackle the questions in the data response section, also larger percent of the candidates show great deficiency in the application of graphical representation to economic analysis and this resulted in poor performance in questions where analyses are required (WAEC 2017; 2020 and 2021). Furthermore, in the WASSCE Chief Examiner's Report, it was identified that the students' weaknesses include; poor graphical representations to economic analysis and simple calculations, use of wrong terminologies, failure to expatiate points, among others (WAEC 2017 & 2018 and NBC/FGN 2022).

Ejimonye, Eneogu and Ugwuanyi (2017) opined that the under-achievement of students in Economics could generally be attributed to students' level of understanding to general aspect of Economics which also assisted with students' level of preparation and readiness for the examination. Ejimonye et al. (2017) discovered that students with poor mathematical and statistical background are usually frightened by mathematical and statistical related subjects, such as Economics. Moreover, the use of wide range of complex mathematics and statistical procedures to analyse Economic phenomena induce students' phobia for the Quantitative Economics, and thereafter affects their overall achievement (Dawson, 2013).

Spring (2013) noted that fluctuations in students' achievement in public examinations could be attributed to several factors which include inadequate learning materials, students' engagement in other hobbies aside schooling, pressure from home, societal factors *etcetera*. WAEC (2007) revealed that students performed poorly due to lack of adequate preparation, shortage of teachers in schools, poor use and inadequate coverage of the syllabus, un-conducive school environment and infrastructural facilities. Others include inability to understand questions that demand high level of thinking, shallow and poor answers to questions due to poor command of English among others. Kola and Sunday (2015) noted that when the foundation at the primary and junior secondary schools is not sound, there will be difficulties in understanding some critical problems in senior secondary schools which automatically lead to failure in examination at the senior secondary schools.

Other empirical studies on students' achievement in Economics revealed that variables such as learners' readiness, engagement in other business apart from schooling, students' poor attitude and poor self-esteem, poor teaching methodology and length of time allocated for reading are equally responsible for the students' persistent under-achievement in senior secondary school Economics (Kola & Sunday, 2015; Obiezu, 2018; Spring, 2013). Although, studies have been pointing toward several factors that have serious implications on students' achievement in Economics at secondary school, but variables that relate to viability of schools which center on school effectiveness have not been adequately and jointly investigated. Therefore, this study intends to investigate some of school effectiveness variables on students' achievements on the quantitative concepts of Economics.

Adewale and Abiodun (2009), while developing and validating teachers' evaluation of school effectiveness scale outlined school administration, school activities, students cognitive domain, inspectorate role, societal expectations, students' empowerment and teachers' job performance as some of the schools' effectiveness variables. Other factors as outlined by other

studies include; school location, school ethos and school learning culture (Reynolds, Teddlie, Creemers & Scheerens, 2019). This study will examine, school administrative practices, school ethos, school learning culture and school activities.

School effectiveness is a construct that is diverse in content; it depends mainly on the direction the researcher is working towards. However, Scheerens (2019) claimed that at the heart of all school effectiveness study is an attempt to explain how school inputs, context of schooling, and school processes affect school's outputs. Also school effectiveness includes the factors input by the school, as well as the processes involved in attaining and achieving meaningful output. Studies on school effectiveness usually center on input-output processes; instructions and materials workability, students' background and location (Akanni, 2020, Dangara, 2016).

School administration is a broad concept that explains all the areas related to school operations as an academic entity. Administrator of school oversees the daily operations of the school and coordinates the schools' system of operations. Suleima, Mustapha and Bukar (2016) referred to school administration as the leadership operations or styles employed by the school leaders (principal and other heads) in the day to day running of the school affairs in order to guide the system to achieve its goals and meet societal expectations (Rusok, Samy & Bhaumik 2023). Similarly, Administrator schedules several activities in the school to keep the system moving towards its stated goals. School administration encompasses categories of administrative practices that aid smooth process of the schools' inputs to achieve the desired outputs that represent the school in the society (Kieti, Maithya & Mulwa 2017). An administrator put many activities together to achieve this, some of it, are regarded as school activities.

School activities are the set of programmes put in place by the School administrators to provide opportunity for the learners or students to be involved in the life of the school, and these are guided by the school norms, beliefs and values. The norms, beliefs and values that are parts of the factors guiding the school activities are regarded as the school ethos. Ethos means custom or character in Greek. It is referred to as the character, custom or personality that balances passion and caution. Graham (2012) defines ethos as the unique pervasive atmosphere or mood of the organisation as it is created from the activities or the behaviour of members through their social interactions and matters associated with the environment. According to some studies, a good school ethos is created by strong academic atmosphere, high expectations for students' success, and positive rewards on landmark achievements (Kjellstrom 2017; Kutsyuruba, Klinger & Hussain 2015; Modin, Laftman & Ostberg 2017). Kutsyuruba *et al.* (2015) explains that school ethos and related notions such as school climate and some school contextual features are recognised as central to students' achievement and well-being.

Warin (2017) asserts that school ethos is also more likely to promote constructive student behaviours and a shared sense of belonging that fosters positive student outcomes. School ethos is the prevalent characteristics, school tone, spirit or sentiment informing an identifiable entity involving human life and interactions, school ethos embraces factors that contribute to the smooth running of the school such as activities and human relations within the school. Smith (2003) maintains that school ethos embraces all aspects of school culture, climate and philosophy that impinge directly on students' affective and cognitive learning which are perceived by all school's stakeholders.

School ethos is experienced at the school's members of staff and students relations level and encompasses the beliefs, values and norms that shape the way that teachers and students relate, interact, and behave towards one another (Modin, Laftman and Ostberg. 2017). It is an aspect of the school's transparent value system, teachers' conduct towards students, as well as the implementation of policies regarding discipline and rewards (Kjellstrom, Holmin, Saenger, Jarl & Modin, 2017, Saminathen, Stephanie & Modin 2020). Therefore, school ethos contributes largely to learning, it is part of what encouraged students to learn effectively; it prepares and empowers students' interactions in the society. Schools with good ethos encourage smooth learning culture for students.

School learning culture has often been considered in terms of the environment and experiences created by teachers for students to learn. Learning culture is the collective, dynamic and experiences that are structured by the organisation's leaders in such a way that the subordinates have opportunities to investigate, explore and take risks in developing new ideas and insights to reach the higher level (Chanani & Wibowo. 2019). School learning culture is based on the experiences which provide templates for future actions based on how we do things in an organisation to produce effective outcome. It often shapes the way people think and how they act. Learning cultures correlate strongly with increased students' achievement and motivation, and with teachers' productivity and satisfaction (Sheela & Claris. 2015).

In a nutshell, school effectiveness variables that include school administrative practices, school activities, school ethos and school learning cultures are considered to be significantly influenced student's achievement in some subjects, but literatures are silent on their contributions to the achievement of students in Economics generally and particularly in Quantitative Economics. This study, therefore, focuses on the connection of the indicator variables of school effectiveness and how they

affect students' achievement in Quantitative Economics in senior secondary schools. Consequently, their relative and holistic contribution in predicting the criterion variable (Academic Achievement of the students in Quantitative Economics).

School is considered as the centre of learning to ease the human living conditions and solve varieties of human challenges, therefore school effectiveness is paramount to students' level of performance in their academic endeavor. Over years studies and reports has been directed towards the fluctuation in the level of academic achievements of students in Economics particularly in the concepts that involve mathematics and statistics that is known as Quantitative Economics. Meanwhile several factors and variables, such as parental background, school location, and Student engagement and so on had been investigated on students' achievement in Economics. But it seems their dearth of literatures on school effectiveness variables and students' academic achievement in Economics, particularly on the students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics.

Therefore, this study investigated the relative and holistic contribution school effectiveness variable (that include school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture and school ethos) on students' academic achievement of in Quantitative Economics.

Objectives of the study

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Investigate the relationship between school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economics.
2. examine school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) as predictors of students' achievement in Quantitative Economic
3. Investigate the most influential school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) in predicting students' achievement in Quantitative Economics.
4. Outline the predictor variables that do not contribute significantly to the prediction model of the study.

Research Questions

In order to guide the study, the following research questions were raised:

1. What type of relationship exists between school effectiveness variables (School Administrative practices, School activities, School learning culture, School ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?
2. Does the obtained regression equation resulting from the set of predictor variables; school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) allow a reliable prediction of students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?
3. Which of the predictors is/are most influential in predicting students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?
4. Are there any predictor variables that do not contribute significantly to the prediction model of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted correlation research design. This design was chosen because the researcher does not have control over the variables as their manifestations have already occurred.

Population, Sampling Techniques and Sample

The target population comprises all the Economics students in secondary schools in Osun state.

Multistage sampling technique was used. The researcher used the already stratified educational district (central, west and east) in the state. Thereafter, four Local Government Areas were purposively selected from each of the three educational districts, totaling twelve Local Government Areas within the State. The Local Government Areas were selected based on location (that is LGAs that have both Urban and Rural areas). Likewise, three schools were purposively selected from the sampled Local Government Areas (two schools from urban and one school from rural and schools that have 35-40 students offering Economics in S.S.S II class). Then thirty S.S.S.II Economics students were randomly selected from each of the sampled schools (totaling ninety students per LGA). And a total of 1080 students were randomly sampled for the study.

Instrumentation

Five instruments were used for the data collection, four of them were validated using Cronbach Alpha; School Administration Practices Scale (SAPS) with reliability coefficient of 0.91, School Activities Scale (SAS) with reliability coefficient of 0.80, School Ethos Questionnaire (SEQ) with reliability coefficient of 0.78 and School Learning Cultures Scale (SLCS) with reliability coefficient of 0.90 while Quantitative Economics Achievement Test was validated using KR20 and the reliability coefficient was 0.88.

Procedure for data Collection and Analysis

The approval to conduct the research was sought and obtained from the schools’ authority. Also, ethical considerations was ensured by telling the students the purpose of the study. Six research assistants were employed; two research assistants was deployed to each district for data collection exercise, the data collection lasted for five weeks. Multiple regressions were used to analyse data collected.

Presentation Of Result

Research Question One

What type of relationship exists between school effectiveness variables (School Administrative practices, School activities, School learning culture, School ethos) and students’ achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?

Table 1: Correlation Matrix of correlation among the variables

	School administrative	School activities	School ethos	School learn culture	Achievement
School Administrative	1				
School activities	.497**	1			
School ethos	-.001	.034	1		
School learn culture	.251**	.169**	.003	1	
Achievement	.224**	.054	.047	.056	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 1 presents the correlation matrix of the variables of the study. It was revealed that, school Administrative Practices has significant positive relationship with School Activities ($r = .497$; $p < .05$), also School Learning culture ($r = .251$; $p < .05$), likewise the School Activities and School learning culture ($r = .169$; $p < .05$). The findings support the outcome of Kieti, Maithya and Mulwa (2017) that school administrative practices correlate significant with student academic performance. The result is also in-line with the findings of Rusok, Samy and Bhaumik (2023) that Learning Culture positively predicts attitude toward academic works. The study equally shows significant relationship between learning culture and school administrative practice.

Research Question Two

Does the obtained regression equation resulting from the set of predictor variables; school effectiveness variables (School Administrative Practices, School Activities, School Learning Culture, School Ethos) allow a reliable prediction of students’ achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?

Table 2: Model Summary of Regression Analysis of School Effectiveness and Academic Achievement in Quantitative Economics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.322 ^a	.104	.101	7.016

a. Predictors: (Constant), SCH_LEARN_CULT, SCH_ETHOS, SCH_ACT, SCH_ADM

Table 3: Analysis of Variance of School effectiveness Variables and Academic Achievement in Quantitative Economics ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6133.972	4	1533.493	31.155	.000 ^b

Residual	52864.232	1074	49.222
Total	58998.204	1078	

a. Dependent Variable: Quantitative Economics Achievement

b. Predictors: (Constant), SCH_LEARN_CULT, SCH_ETHOS, SCH_ACT, SCH_ADM

Tables 2 and 3 present the model summary and ANOVA representatively. The multiple regression correlation coefficient (R) showing the linear relationship between school effectiveness variables (school administrative practices, school activities, school learning culture, school ethos) and students' achievement in Quantitative Economic as shown in Table 2, R is 0.322, the multiple R² is 0.104, and Adjusted R square value is 0.101. This means that the variation in students' achievement in Quantitative Economic accounted for by the predictor variables is approximately 32.2% and it is statistically significant. Moreover Table 3, shows the analysis of variance of the multiple regression data. This produced an F-ratio of $f(4,1078) = 31.155$ and found to be significant at 0.05 Alpha level.

The finding of the study corroborate Ramberg, Laftman, Almquist and Modin (2019) that School effectiveness variables significantly predict students' perceptions of teacher caring, also the finding is in-line with Akanni (2020) that organizational leadership and culture influence the students' performance in south-western Nigeria. Moreover, the school effectiveness variable (school activities) play a significant role in improving students' attendance and engagements in the school (Munir & Zaheer, 2021).

Research Question Three

Which of the predictors is/are most influential in predicting students' achievement in Quantitative Economic in Public Secondary Schools?

Table 4: Relative contributions of School effectiveness Variables to Students' Academic Achievement in Quantitative Economics

Coefficients ^a						
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error				
1	(Constant)	70.936	2.871		24.706	.000
	SCH_ADM	-.113	.033	-.116	-3.410	.001
	SCH_ACT	-.303	.052	-.193	-5.794	.000
	SCH_ETHOS	-.128	.060	-.062	-2.140	.033
	SCH_LEARN_CULT	-.175	.047	-.112	-3.759	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Quantitative Economics Achievement

Table 4 shows the contribution of each of the independent variables to the prediction model and to the 32.2% of the variation of student's achievement in quantitative economics. Meanwhile all the independent variables contributed significantly to the prediction model at 0.05 Alpha level. School activities ($\beta = -.303$; $t(1074) = -5.794$ and school learning culture ($\beta = -.175$; $t(1074) = -3.759$ contributed the highest while school ethos ($\beta = -.128$; $t(1074) = -2.140$). The findings shows that school learning culture and school activities contributed highest to the prediction. And the finding correlated the outcome of Qian, Allan and Yang (2016) that building school learning culture assisted the teacher in improving primary school and promoting positive and progressive learning outcome in primary schools. Also the finding is in-line with Akanni (2020) that organizational leadership and culture influence the students' performance in south-western Nigeria. Kieti, Maithya, & Mulwa (2017) findings also supported that school Administrative Practices significantly predicts Students' academic performance in Public Secondary Schools in Matungulu sub-country, Kenya. The finding also support Rusok, Samy and Bhaumik (2023) that Learning Culture contributed to Innovative and Attitude toward Work.

Research Question Four

Are there any predictor variables that do not contribute significantly to the prediction model of the study?

All the school effectiveness variables contributed significantly to the criterion variable (students' Achievement in Quantitative Economics), but school ethos contributed the lowest. This means that school ethos is significant but not as significantly contributed as other variables. The finding contradict the study of Saminathen, Stephanie and Modin (2020) that the school ethos and Academic Achievement highly predict Adolescent Distress and Aggression in the Segregated School Landscape of Stockholm.

Conclusion

It is obvious that school effectiveness variable contributed significantly to the predictions of the students' academic achievement in Quantitative Economics in Osun state, the variables in the study that includes school administrative practices, schools activities, school learning culture and school ethos that are considered as the new areas of school effectiveness significantly predicted the students' academic achievement in quantitative economics. The findings of the study shows that school effectiveness variables cannot be divorced of its impact on the students' academic achievement in quantitative economics.

Recommendations

The following steps are recommended

1. School administrative practice should be adequately set by the school leaders towards improving the students' academic achievement.
2. School activities as an important aspect of school effectiveness should not be administratively overlook particularly the aspects that deals with engagement of student in calculation as this will have more impact on the achievement in Quantitative Economics.
3. School learning culture should be officially guided by the school by provide templates for future actions based on how we do things in an organisation to produce effective outcome, and teachers should be exposed to their activities involvement on way to provide and follows school learning culture.

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